

Initiators of Redox Polymerization

Ranjit S. Konar and Santi R. Palit

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The important observation was made in 1946 independently by Bacon¹, Evans and co-workers^{2,18}, Morgan³, and others that an oxidation-reduction reaction can efficiently initiate polymerization. Such polymerization is called redox polymerization, the oxidant being often called the catalyst or initiator and the reductant, the activator. Some of the special features of redox polymerization are: (i) induction period is very short, (ii) a comparatively high molecular weight and high yield of polymers can be obtained in a very short time, (iii) activation energy is very small, (iv) the polymerization can be carried out at room temperature or below. An outcome of the redox-initiated polymerization is that it provides a direct experimental evidence of the existence of transient radical intermediates, generated in redox reactions, and identification of these radical end-groups in the resulting polymer throws new light on the reaction mechanism of redox reactions. It is the purpose of the present article to review the various redox systems, which have been used in such polymerization, with special reference to the initiating radical, and identification thereof by methods recently developed in this laboratory^{7,9,4}.

General Reaction Mechanism of Free Radical Initiated Polymerization

As the name suggests, the initiating species of the type of vinyl polymerization is essentially a free radical, generated in the redox reaction, and the reaction mechanism is governed by the laws of free radical reactions (*i.e.* chain reaction). Three steps are involved, e.g., initiation, propagation, and termination. But the fundamental difference between the chain reactions involved in vinyl polymerization and in classical hydrogen-chlorine combination lies in the fact that in the latter case chain carriers have the same size, but in the former case, chain carriers have different sizes, although it is assumed that radical reactivity is independent of chain length in polymerization processes.

If R· be a free radical, and M be a monomeric entity, the steps of the chain reaction are:

Besides, termination may also take place by chain transfer to monomer, to solvent, or to any reactive species like catalyst, activator, inhibitor, or retarder molecules and even by collision between a chain radical and a primary radical, generated from redox reactions.

The free radicals may be neutral or charged. For example,

In both cases, Fe^{2+} ion donates one electron to a molecule of the oxidant, as a result of which the latter becomes thermodynamically unstable and breaks up with the production of a radical.

These radicals open the double bond of the molecules of vinyl monomer ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}$ or $\text{CH}_2=\text{CXY}$) and thereby attach themselves to the end of the polymer chains as end groups. The presence of these end groups or initiator fragments in polymer chains has been proved by tracer technique^{5,9,81}, chemical analysis⁶, and recently by 'dye' partition test^{7,90}.

Some Aspects of Aqueous Polymerization

Redox-initiated vinyl polymerization in aqueous medium may be of two types, e.g., polymerization of (i) water-soluble monomers within their solubility range and (ii) both water-soluble and water-insoluble monomers in presence of detergents.

The nature of the polymerization reactions depends on the structure of the monomer, the affinity of the monomer to its polymer, degree of swelling of the polymer with its monomer, etc. It has been noted that monomers like vinyl acetate, methyl methacrylate, methylacrylate, etc. can be polymerised up to 90 to 92% conversion, but acrylonitrile cannot be polymerised beyond 40 to 45% conversion whatever may be the nature of the redox species. This low conversion is possibly due to the fact that the monomer concentration at the reaction site is low, as the polyacrylonitrile particles are not at all swollen by acrylonitrile monomer, only a very small fraction of it gets adsorbed on them^{9,90}. Again, vinyl acetate polymerises at a faster rate than any other water-soluble monomer, even faster than methyl acrylate, which is possibly due to both polar and steric factors and to the differences in resonance stabilization of the monomer and the radical. The rate of styrene polymerization is comparatively slow, possibly due to the resonance stability of the propagating styryl radical, and lastly ethylene polymerization is a very difficult job. Thus the structure of the monomer plays an important role in polymerization.

Apart from the monomeric entity, other rate-controlling factors are: (1) redox pair, (2) pH of the medium¹, (3) temperature, (4) agitation after initiation, (5) oxygen content of the medium, etc. The separating phase after initiation also plays a very important role in heterogeneous polymerization. If the separating phase is a fine sol, the rate will be higher than that of the case when the separating phase is a coarse coagulum⁹. Polymerization rate generally increases with the rise of temperature as is expected from the Arrhenius theory, but many conflicting reports are available in the literature. For example, Bacon¹ and Whitby *et al.*¹⁰ reported that the rate of polymerization would rise with temperature, whereas work in our laboratory¹¹ shows that the rate of polymerization attains a maximum value at 45° and then falls with further rise in temperature. This discrepancy is pos-

sibly due to the nature of the initiator used and degree of stability of the separating phase. Agitation after initiation depresses the rate, as has been reported by many workers¹², which is probably due to aggregation of the particles carrying the reaction loci.

Detergents function in two ways, viz., (1) they increase the solubility of the monomer by emulsifying it¹³ and (2) they protect the polymer particles from coalescence by acting as peptisers^{3,14}. Thus detergent action is purely physical and the kinetics of methyl methacrylate polymerization remains the same in presence and absence of cetavlon¹⁴, provided that the monomer concentration exceeds its solubility in the aqueous phase. But Kolthoff and Miller¹⁵ showed that fatty acid soaps, when used as emulsifier in emulsion polymerizations using $K_2S_2O_8$ as initiator, underwent chemical change such as decarboxylation.

Initiation by Redox-reaction Involving One-electron Change

To this class belong both organic and inorganic peroxide systems, hydroperoxide systems, and systems containing non-peroxidic substances as redox components.

Hydrogen Peroxide Systems.—Evans and his school² studied Fenton's reagent ($FeSO_4-H_2O_2$) as a redox initiator where $\cdot OH$ radicals are known to be the chain-initiating species. The mechanism of this redox reaction is primarily due to Haber and Weiss¹⁶. In presence of monomer, there is a competition between the monomer and the unchanged ferrous ions for consuming the hydroxyl radicals. In presence of a sufficient amount of monomer, no evolution of oxygen occurs and ferrous ions react according to equation (i). In the absence of monomer, the reaction takes place as follows, where (i) is the initiation reaction, (ii) and (iii) or (ii), (iv) and (v) are the chain decomposition of H_2O_2 , (vi) is chain termination, and (vii) is the initiation of polymerization.

Evans and coworkers¹⁷ showed that oxidation of glycolic acid by $FeSO_4-H_2O_2$ was greatly reduced in presence of acrylonitrile. This indicates that $\cdot OH$ radicals are responsible for both polymerization and oxidation.

Again, if $\cdot OH$ radicals be the chain-initiating species, OH groups must be present in the polymer as end groups. This has been proved by Evans¹⁸ by infrared absorption spectra¹⁹ and recently in our laboratory by the 'dye partition test'²⁰.

Barb *et al.*²⁵ modified the Haber-Weiss mechanism and showed that oxygen evolved according to the following reaction, and not due to reaction (iii).

Fe^{2+} — H_2O_2 system, however, does not always initiate polymerization. For example, Barb *et al.*⁹⁵ failed to initiate acrylonitrile polymerization under the following conditions: (1) Fe^{2+} concentration = 10^{-4} , H_2O_2 conc. = $1.0 M$, $\text{pH} = 1$, and $N/5$ acrylonitrile at 25° . The excess hydrogen peroxide removes the hydroxyl radicals from the medium according to reaction (ii), and $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ radicals, thus formed, do not initiate vinyl polymerization. In other words, at a fixed concentration of the activator, there is a fixed concentration of catalyst for polymerization to occur. Marvel *et al.*²¹ studied copolymerization of butadiene and styrene, whereas Kern²² reported the same copolymerization using H_2O_2 — Fe^{2+} ions—sorbose as initiator. Like Fe (II) salts, Fe (III) salts are also effective in activating hydrogen peroxide; both the salts are equivalent in their activating effect²¹.

According to Marvel *et al.*²¹ the reaction between ferric ions and hydrogen peroxide is believed to be as follows:

Dainton *et al.*^{9,120} studied acrylonitrile polymerization initiated by Fenton's reagent. They noted that whenever ferric salts were either present initially or generated *in situ*, some polyacrylonitrile radicals were always destroyed by Fe^{3+} ions. The rate of polymerization is proportional to the square of the monomer concentration at low monomer concentrations and linearly dependent on monomer concentration at high monomer concentrations.

Hydrogen peroxide has also been activated by various reducing agents. It appears that the mechanism is essentially the same, involving $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals. Some such typical activating agents are ammonia or aliphatic amines²³, sodium nitrite²⁴, formic acid and ferrous ammonium sulphate²³, acetic acid and ferrous sulphate²⁵, Rongalite²⁷, ferric nitrate^{27a}, ferrous ammonium sulphate in presence of potassium palmitate, E.D.T.A. and other complexing agents^{27b}, and peroxidase^{27c}. Bacon¹ reported activation of H_2O_2 by NaHSO_3 in the polymerization of acrylonitrile in aqueous solution. Kern *et al.*²⁵ reported acrolein polymerization using (i) hydrogen peroxide-ferrous ammonium sulphate, (ii) H_2O_2 — AgNO_3 , and (iii) H_2O_2 — NaNO_2 , as redox initiators.

In the system H_2O_2 — CH_3COOH — FeSO_4 , the radicals are both $\cdot\text{OH}$ and $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$, the presence of the latter having been proved in our laboratory by the dye-test²⁴. This accounts for the observed retarding action of acetic acid on the Fe^{2+} — H_2O_2 reaction²⁶.

Persulphates.—Persulphates, either alone or with activators, have been extensively used as initiators of redox polymerization. Bacon¹ activated persulphate using various reducing agents, viz., metals, oxidisable metal salts, hydrazine, hydroxylamine, hydrogen sulphide, thiols, salts of various oxyacids of sulphur (sulphite, dithionite and thiosulphate), and polyhydric phenols. Kern⁴ also reported similar observations. Kolthoff *et al.*²⁸ and Williams *et al.*²⁹ studied the kinetics of polymerization initiated by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — Fe^{2+} ions. Activation of persulphates has also been done by ferricyanide³⁰ and various cobalt complexes³¹. The details of the reactions are not available; the system is also very complex as these multivalent metal ions can initiate polymerization without the aid of peroxidic substances^{32,33}. Tervalent silver, when added in the form of biguanide complex³⁶, can initiate polymerization of acrylonitrile and methyl methacrylate³⁴. Silver ion—persulphate (Ag^+ — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$) is also a very useful redox initiator and has been used by many workers^{1,3,7c,33}.

In copolymerization of styrene and butadiene, the initiators that have been used extensively are thiol-persulphate³⁴ and bisulphite-persulphate³⁵. Some metal ions and also anions act as promoters in the two-component 'reduction-activation' of persulphates, e.g., Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , I^- ions in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ system³, Fe^{2+} in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — HSO_3^- (used for tetrafluoroethylene³⁹ polymerization) and silver (used for chlorotrifluoroethylene⁴⁰ polymerization). Roskin⁴¹ used the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ redox pair; Palit and Guha⁴³ and Palit and Biswas⁴⁴ used the same for aqueous redox polymerization. Acrolein has been polymerised by the initiator $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — SO_3^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — NO_2^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — Ag^+ , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — Ti^{3+} by Kern *et al.*⁴².

As to the mechanism of initiation, the general trend is to assume an electron transfer as in Fenton's reaction, giving rise to an $\cdot\text{SO}_4^-$ ion radical, e.g.,

The initiation by $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals has also been suggested by Morgan³ and Whitby *et al.*¹⁰ in the Ag^+ — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ system, but others consider $\cdot\text{SO}_4^-$ to be the initiating radical¹. Roskin⁴¹ also propounds the $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical in the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ system.

Eager and Winkler³⁶ studied the kinetics of the thiol-persulphate reaction in homogeneous aqueous solution and formulated it as:

Levitt³⁶ believed that sulphur tetroxide was an intermediate product in this reaction. Like thiols, thiol-esters³⁷ and diaroyl disulphides³⁷ may be used in the activation of persulphate in the copolymerization of butadiene and styrene. Kolthoff *et al.*³⁸ also used persulphate-thiol redox in the emulsion polymerization of vinyl monomer. Campbell³⁶ studied polymerization of acrylonitrile, initiated by $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ — NaHSO_3 , in presence of various complexing agents for iron, which is always present as trace impurities in the catalyst, and the activator. He demonstrated that $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — HSO_3^- reaction would always require a trace of iron as catalyst. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ —ferrous ammonium sulphate has been used in the polymerization of methylvinyl ketone¹⁰.

It may be pointed out that the evidence for the varied types of suggested initiating radical had so far been highly conjectural, resting on kinetic evidence based on non-reproducible data. Direct evidence has been lacking except in a few cases where the existence of sulphur in the polymer has been demonstrated and even measured, using tracer techniques⁵. The position has lately become, however, more definite by the development in our laboratory of two simple methods^{7,9,4} of detection of end groups by interaction with dyes. The results of end-group detection show that SO_4^- radicals are not necessarily the initiator in many redox systems containing $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. For example, we have found that polymers, obtained by initiation with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ alone and HCOO^- — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ system, contain no strong acid end group, but $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — Ag^+ , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ — $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ initiated polymers give positive test for strong acid end group. The question seems to be an intriguing one and the matter is being closely investigated in our laboratory.

Organic Peroxide and Hydroperoxide Systems.—The initiation of vinyl polymerization by organic peroxide systems is primarily due to the German workers and later on by the American workers for industrial processes. Kern^{4,41} has reported a large number of redox systems containing benzoyl peroxide. The general reaction mechanism in the three-

component systems (organic peroxide— Fe^{2+} ions—a reducing agent YH_2) is believed to be as follows:

When the reducing agent does not react with Fe^{3+} ions, the metal ions function by complex formation with the reducing agent (e.g., benzoyl peroxide— Fe^{3+} ions—tertiary amine⁴⁵):

The chain initiating species are $\text{RCOO}\cdot$ radicals⁴⁶. Marvel *et al.*⁴⁷ and Johnson and Bebb⁴⁸ studied copolymerization of butadiene and styrene using benzoyl peroxide and acetyl peroxide systems. The reducing agents of the three-component peroxide systems are α -ketols, benzoin, dihydroxyacetone, or preferably ketoses (sorbitose and fructose). Wall and Swoboda⁴⁹ have used benzoyl peroxide—iron pyrophosphate—sorbitose as redox initiator. This system has also been studied by Kolthoff *et al.*⁵⁰.

The bulk polymerization of vinyl monomers by redox pairs like benzoyl peroxide and a reducing agent like sulphinic acids, α -ketols, formic acid, thiols, hydrazines, and tertiary amine had been studied⁴⁵. The activity of such systems is greatly enhanced by the introduction of a soluble metal salt (salts of Pb, Fe, Co, Ni, Mn, Cu, Zn, Ce).

Hasegawa *et al.*⁵¹ studied vinyl acetate polymerization using benzoyl peroxide— Fe^{2+} ions—benzoin system. Kern⁵² studied styrene polymerization using the same system. Tobolsky *et al.*⁵³ and O'Driscoll *et al.*⁵⁴ studied 'Dead end polymerization' of vinyl monomers using benzoyl peroxide—dimethylaniline as redox pair. This redox pair has also been used by many other workers^{91,92,93} for studying the polymerization of styrene and methyl methacrylate.

Hydroperoxide Systems.—Like organic peroxides, hydroperoxides (e.g. cumene hydroperoxide) have been used extensively in vinyl polymerization in presence of a suitable reducing agent. In presence of metal ions as reducing agent, the hydroperoxide is decomposed as a free radical⁵⁵⁻⁵⁶.

But in alkaline medium, decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide by Fe^{2+} ions has been reported to be ionic in character⁵⁷.

A large number of reducing agents have been used in conjunction with cumene hydroperoxide and iron salts, e.g., dihydroxyacetone, sodium sulphide, hydrazine, sodium formaldehyde sulphonylate⁵⁸. Cumene hydroperoxide— Fe^{2+} salts—sugar also has been used in styrene—butadiene copolymerization⁵⁹. Fe-salts have been used in the form of pyrophosphate⁵⁹ or E.D.T.A. complex⁶⁰.

Kolthoff *et al.*⁶¹ studied a complicated reaction involving isopropyl- α -dimethylbenzyl hydroperoxide—nitroprusside—hydroxylamine—thiol as initiator of polymerization. Orr and Williams⁶² studied the reaction kinetics of cumene hydroperoxide—Fe²⁺ salts—amine (e.g. diethylenediamine, triethylenetetramine, or tetraethylenepentamine) in presence and absence of methyl methacrylate and found that Fe²⁺ ions formed complexes with the amine; this complex subsequently reacted with the hydroperoxide.

Isopropylbenzene hydroperoxide—SO₂ redox system has been used in emulsion polymerization⁶³. Polyamines [NH₂—(CH₂·CH₂NH)_n—H],—cumene hydroperoxide—Fe²⁺ salts have also been used as initiator of polymerization⁷⁰.

System Containing Air or Oxygen.—The role of oxygen in aqueous and emulsion polymerization of vinyl monomers has been discussed by Kern⁴ and by Bovey and Kolthoff⁶⁴, and recently by Dainton⁶. It has been established that induction period in polymerization is primarily due to oxygen, which thus acts as an inhibitor. But if the reducing agent of the redox system is reactive towards oxygen, the induction period will be shortened and the oxygen will behave as a co-catalyst. Sully⁶⁵ reported that the emulsion polymerization of styrene was promoted by sulphite in presence of traces of air and copper salt

The Cu⁺ ions are again reoxidised by air. We have also noted that potassium bisulphite in presence of traces of air can initiate polymerization of methyl methacrylate, strong acid end groups having been detected in the polymer⁶⁴. The probable reaction is

German workers⁶⁶ have studied copolymerization of butadiene—styrene, using oxygen as sole oxidant in different redox systems. The reducing agents were dithionite, sulphinic acids, thiols and α -ketols, promoted by iron pyrophosphate. Marvel⁶⁷ extended the same work, using cobalt salt as additional catalyst and long chain alkane-1-sulphinic acid as a reducing agent.

Hydrazine—Cu⁺ ions—oxygen has been used as a three-component redox initiator by Menon and Kapur⁶⁸. The reactive species are believed to be hydrazyl radicals.

Oxygen also acts as a chain-terminating agent by forming peroxides^{2,4,69}.

Non-peroxidic Systems.—Fe³⁺—HSO₃⁻ and Fe³⁺—S₂O₃²⁻ systems have also been used as redox initiators⁷¹. The probable reactions are:

We have also used Fe³⁺—S₂O₃²⁻ system for initiation of methyl methacrylate polymerization in aqueous solution, strong acid end groups having been detected in polymers⁶⁴.

Davies *et al.*⁷³ reported that hydroxylamine—titanous/chromous salt in acid solution could initiate polymerization and they proved that initiation was due to ·NH₂ radicals.

Evans and co-workers⁷⁴ showed that Fe^{3+} salts—hypobromous acid could initiate polymerization and that bromine atoms initiated the chain reaction.

Acrylonitrile^{75, 1} was polymerized by the redox pair, trimethylamine and chlorine.

Ceric nitrate—3-chloro-1-propanol has been used in the initiation of acrylamide⁷⁶. Ceric salts and organic reducing agents, e.g., alcohols, thiols, glycols, aldehydes, and amines, have been used in the preparation of graft copolymer⁷⁷. Ceric ion proceeds *via* a single-electron transfer with the formation of free radicals on the reducing agent⁷⁷.

Ceric ion—alcohol (e.g. ethyl, amyl, etc.) has been used for the initiation of vinyl monomers by Santhapa *et al*⁷⁷.

Methyl methacrylate has been polymerized by xanthine oxidase (OX) and formaldehyde⁷⁸.

Peroxidase— H_2O_2 has also been used as polymerization initiator⁷⁹. *N*-Nitrosoacetanilide and ferrous versenate or citrate⁸⁰ have been used in the emulsion polymerization of styrene and in the styrene—butadiene emulsion copolymerization. Diazonium compounds and metal ions⁸¹ can also initiate vinyl polymerization.

Reactions Involving Multi-electron Change

In this system the oxidant must contain an atom existing in a higher state of oxidation, e.g., Mn in permanganate and MnO_2 , Cl in chlorate and chlorite, Br in bromate, etc. Kern⁴ reported that German workers used chlorate, hypochlorite, permanganate, or manganese dioxide as the oxidising agent of redox initiators, but details are not available.

Kolthoff and Meehan⁷¹ reported that initiation of butadiene-styrene copolymerization could be done by unstable ionic species. They used chromate-arsenite system for initiation and proposed the following redox reaction:

Possibly both Cr^{4+} and Cr^{5+} ions are the initiating species.

Thomas *et al.*⁸⁰ studied acrylonitrile polymerization kinetically, using $\text{ClO}_3^- - \text{SO}_3^{2-}$ system in acid solution. Firsching and Rosen⁸¹ used $\text{ClO}_3^- - \text{HSO}_3^-$ redox, and they, by using tracer techniques, showed that the initiating species were $\cdot\text{SO}_3^-$ and $\text{Cl}\cdot$ radicals.

We have used a large number of redox initiators containing permanganate as the oxidising agent. The reducing agents are oxalic acid^{82,90} citric acid, tartaric acid, isobutyric acid, glycerol⁹⁰, bisulphite⁸⁴ (in presence of dilute H_2SO_4), hydrosulphite⁸⁴ (in presence dilute H_2SO_4), etc. In case of organic acids, carboxyl end groups⁷ have been identified in polymers, OH end groups⁷ in case of glycerol as reduction activator, and strong acid end groups⁸⁴ in case of bisulphite, sulphite and hydrosulphite. The peculiarity of the permanganate system is that there are two consecutive redox systems in presence of monomer⁸³, viz., (1) permanganate (oxidant) and monomer (reductant); and (2) separated manganese dioxide (oxidant) and added reducing agent (reductant).

In case of permanganate—oxalic acid, the reactive species may be any one of the following: carboxyl ion radical, oxalate ion radical, ($\text{HCO}_2\cdot$, $\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4\cdot$) and possibly the radical containing manganese, as postulated by Duke^{83a}. This is consistent with the fact that the reaction solution absorbs oxygen⁸³.

We also noted that freshly prepared $\text{MnO}_2 - \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ is a very good redox initiator, sulphate end groups having been detected in the polymers⁸⁴.

This $\dot{\text{S}}\text{O}_4^-$ radical possibly initiates the polymer chain. $\text{KBrO}_3 - \text{KHSO}_3$, and $\text{KBrO}_3 - \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3 - \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ redox systems⁸⁴ can also initiate polymerization, giving rise to strong acid end groups in the polymer.

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